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The Help-Seeking Behavior of Male College Students in Kabankalan Catholic College

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Abstract

This study is intended to understand extent of help-seeking behavior of male college students. This study used descriptive quantitative research design. The participants were the male college students of the College Department of Kabankalan Catholic College, enrolled in the Academic Year 2022 - 2023. Moreover, this study used Attitude Toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help Test, a standardized instrument measuring the help-seeking behavior of the participants. The results revealed that male college students opt to seek psychological help when they are psychologically distressed. Moreover, it was also found out that the perception towards seeking help in matters pertaining to the time needed for the process hinders the participants to seek help. In addition, help-seeking inside the institution is free and readily accessible, yet the data gathered shown that participants still thought that to seek help may cost them a lot. Awareness for access to where the participants can seek help could be a great factor of this occurrence. Thus, the study suggests that further investigation discussing the factors of help-seeking behavior of certain population is significant to shed light on this phenomenon. Furthermore, this study highly recommends to all institutions to initiate programs and projects that will help combat the misconception of seeking help to the appropriate professionals in order to continuously promote accessible psychological help to all.

Keywords: *help-seeking behavior, male, college student, attitude toward seeking professional psychological help test*

Introduction

Gender significantly impacts the way people seek help, with studies showing that men are less likely to seek treatment for mental health issues compared to women (Mojtabai et al., 2016; Ogan et al., 2014). Gender stands out as a major predictor affecting individuals' help-seeking behavior (Jacoby & Li, 2022). Men who internalize societal stigma about mental health tend to avoid seeking help, facing greater challenges and a heightened risk for severe mental illness (Mckenzie et al., 2022). Moreover, males tend to be less receptive to professional assistance, while females are twice as likely to express intent and persistence in seeking treatment for depression and other mental health issues (Biggers & Leonard, 2021; Liddon et al., 2018).

Research often suggests that traditional masculine ideals, such as strength, success, independence, control, and capability, along with a tendency to avoid emotional expression, contribute to men's reluctance to seek help for depression (Staiger et al., 2022). In 2017, Great Britain recorded almost 6000 suicides, with men comprising 75% of these cases (Mental Health Foundation, 2021). In the Philippines, around 3.6 million individuals deal with mental, neurological, or substance disorders, with a suicide rate of 3.2% per 100,000 people, notably higher among males (Department of Health, 2020; Martinez et al., 2020). Mental illness ranks as the third most prevalent disability in the Philippines.

Male college students are hesitant to seek psychological help, viewing it as weak. Men's help-seeking behavior is understudied in sociology, psychology, and other academic disciplines. In Asia, particularly the Philippines, studies focus on men's roles and gender, not men's help-seeking behavior. This study, therefore, intends to determine the extent of help-seeking behaviors of male college students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of help-seeking behaviors of male college students for the academic year 2022-2023. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents when grouped according to:
 - 1.1 age; and
 - 1.2 program cluster?
2. What is the extent of the help-seeking behavior of the participants towards seeking professional help?

Literature Review

This section presents a review of related literature. Specifically, this section deals with the conceptually related literature and related studies on men's help-seeking behavior.

Help-seeking Behaviors

Help-seeking behavior involves seeking suitable treatment for health issues (Pianta et al., 2020). Many teenagers with mental health issues fail to seek professional care, but it's essential for overall well-being and preventing mental health disorders (Pearson & Hyde,

2021). Men, who view health as crucial for their "male responsibilities," are less likely to seek mental health care, leading to higher rates of suicide compared to women (Sagar-Ouriaghi et al., 2020; Idris et al., 2019).

Johnson (2018) found a positive correlation between masculinity, self-stigma, and men's assistance seeking. Men are less likely to seek psychological help when exhibiting symptoms, but more likely to advocate for friends or strangers. Martinez et al. (2020) found Filipino resilience and self-reliance hindering mental health assistance, while Shi et al. (2020) found barriers to professional help-seeking in mental health.

Internationally, in the study of Adams et al. (2022), a significant public health issue is mental health. According to recent prevalence rate, 10.7% of people worldwide suffer from a mental health disorder increased by 13.5% between 2007 and 2017. These changes are probably the result of rising prevalence rates and greater life expectancies. Unaddressed mental health needs not only increase the time that a person must deal with the consequences of poor mental health, but are also associated with greater levels of disability, a lower quality of life and an increased risk of suicidal thoughts and attempts.

Locally, in the study of Martinez et al. (2020) on Filipino's help-seeking for mental health problems, Filipino attitude of resilience and self-reliance hinders them from asking mental health assistance. They only seek assistance on mental health care when the conditions are severe.

Mental Health trends Amongst College Students

Students struggling with depression and anxiety face increased risks of dropping out, poor academic performance, substance use, and suicide. 75% are reluctant to seek help, and four out of five college students have clear warning signs before attempting suicide (Druckenmiller, 2022).

Men need to enhance positive behavior and communication, as gender roles change. A crisis in masculinity arises as men struggle to embrace good masculinities and achieve gender justice, influenced by various factors (Boopalan, 2018).

The American Psychological Association released a statement at the same time. Issued updated recommendations for therapists dealing with boys and men, noting that extreme variations of some aggression, misogyny, and poor health are all linked to "typical" masculine qualities (Salter, 2019).

Help-seeking Stigma

The stigma surrounding seeking treatment for mental health issues among men contributes to higher suicide rates. Men are often viewed as weak and may refuse treatment due to traditional masculine ideals (Grewal, 2020). Due to this, obtaining treatment becomes more difficult for men. When males ask for assistance, it violates traditional masculine ideals since it takes away their ability to solve a problem on their own (Johnson, 2018). Moreso, in order to avoid being called "mentally ill" or "unmanly," men with depressive symptoms may refuse treatment, and self-stigmatization or guilt might weaken motivation to seek help (Staiger et al, 2020). According to Hall (2021) study on Arab Men's Attitudes Toward Health Issues and Help Seeking, rather than seeking professional assistance from what they perceived to be Western therapies, the men in the study seemed to place a lot of emphasis on how close their family and community were to them and thought that this was a preferred way to handle issues like anger and sadness.

Trend of Seeking Professional Help

Masculinity has an impact on health-seeking behavior. Men's use of health services continues to reflect the association between masculinity and health-seeking behavior (Tseole & Vermaak, 2020). According to Staiger et al. (2020), men's help-seeking behavior before seeking therapy was adversely impacted by internalized male norms. Discrimination against people with mental illnesses due to their condition has a detrimental effect on their ability to access mental health services, engage in help-seeking behaviors, and receive initial treatment. As a result, this discrimination raises the morbidity and mortality rates of people with mental illnesses (Chatmon, 2020).

Synthesis

The above-cited studies examined the help-seeking behavior of male college students. It highlights that help-seeking behavior for mental health issues is hindered by stigma and adherence to traditional masculine norms, leading to potential negative consequences. Cultural factors also play a role, with an emphasis on familial and community support. This review underscores the need to address these challenges to promote better mental health outcomes.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized descriptive quantitative design. The variables in quantitative descriptive research are quantified using numerical terms, but the researcher does not influence the variables being studied. It is a non-experimental style of research. According to studies on descriptive research, which categorizes different types of research based on their "purpose of research," this type of research is frequently referred to as descriptive research. The word "quantitative" is used to underline that the variables in our discussion are

measured in numerical terms (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019).

Participants

We utilized stratified sampling procedure under probability sampling in determining the student-respondents.

The population of the participants was 358 from various courses of the College Department of Kabankalan Catholic College. 186 or 52% served as the sample of the study.

Table 1 below shows the distribution of samples in every course of the respondents.

Distribution of Participants

<i>Academic Program College of Education</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>
Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED)	20	10
Bachelor of Secondary Education – Major in English (BSED English)	22	12
Bachelor of Secondary Education – Major in Math (BSED Filipino)	12	6
Bachelor of Secondary Education – Major in Science (BSED Science)	3	2
Bachelor of Physical Education (BPED)	28	15
Subtotal	123	65
<i>College of Business and Accountancy</i>		
Bachelor of Science in Business Management –Marketing Management (BSBA MM)	37	19
Bachelor of Science in Business Management –Financial Management (BSBA FM)	41	21
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA)	10	5
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT)	111	58
Subtotal	199	103
<i>College of Arts and Sciences</i>		
Bachelor of Science in Psychology (BSP)	18	9
Bachelor of Arts in Philosophy (ABP)	18	9
Subtotal	36	18
Total	358	186

Instruments

This study used a standardized instrument to know the extent of help-seeking behavior of male college students. This study used the Attitudes Toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help (ATSPPH) to measure the help-seeking behavior of the participants. The ATSPPH will be the instrument used to measure the participants' help-seeking behavior. The mean range and verbal interpretation are modified by the researchers to attain an apt and exact data needed.

<i>Mean Range</i>	<i>Difference</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1.00 – 1.85	0.85	Very untrue of me
1.86 – 2.71	0.85	Untrue of me
2.72 – 3.57	0.85	Somewhat untrue of me
3.58 – 4.43	0.85	Neutral
4.44 – 5.29	0.85	Somewhat true of me
5.30 – 6.15	0.85	True of me
6.16 – 7.00	0.84	Very true of me

Attitudes Toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help (ATSPPH). Questionnaire. Participants' attitudes towards seeking professional psychological help for mental health issues were gauged using a short form of the 29-item Attitudes toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help Scale. Participants were asked to indicate their level of agreement with the statement made (e.g., personal and emotional troubles, like many things, tend to work out by themselves) in each item on a scale of 1 (Strongly disagree) to 7 (Strongly agree).

Procedure

Prior to the administration of the survey, we first sought permission from the researchers' mentor in Research in Psychology 1 subject, to the Vice President of the Academic Affairs, Deans of the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS), College of Teacher Education (COED), and College of Business and Accountancy (CBA). The sample size was 186 students and determined through a Raosoft calculator and a stratified sampling procedure will randomly select the respondents. The student-participants were male college students from first – fourth year across the three (3) program clusters of the college department. The participants answered the Attitude Toward Seeking Professional Psychological Help, that measures the participant's help-seeking behavior, adapted from Levant et al. (2020).

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of the study, we assure the utmost recognition of confidentiality in all information gathered (McClelland & Bruckert, 2022). Whereas, in this study, participants were given an informed consent that provides sufficient information and assurances about

taking part to allow individuals to understand the implications of participation and to reach a fully informed, considered, and freely given decision about whether to do so, without the exercise of any pressure or coercion (Rennie et al., 2022). The researchers sent a voluntary informed consent to the participants for their privacy and confidentiality in the study. Moreover, participants were informed that their involvement in the research is entirely voluntary and that they may quit at any time without consequence (Zhang, 2023). The results are confidential; however, it was repeated that no personally identifiable data will be released if the research is presented or published.

Results

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. The data gathered in the study were subjected to the following statistical treatments.

For problem number 1, to better illustrate the distribution of participants across different age range and program cluster, the researchers used the frequency and percentage. Frequency distribution is how frequently various scores appear within a sample of scores. It is used frequently to group data according to categories that allow for visual interpretation (Cherry, 2021). Also, percentage is a quantity or a ratio that is represented as a fraction of 100. Calculating a percentage involves multiplying a value by 100 and dividing it by the population as a whole. Thus, percent can be interpreted as a portion per hundred (Shwetha, 2023). For problem number 2, to show the extent of help-seeking behavior of the participants, mean was also used in order to analyze the gathered data.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the male college students

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age		
19-21 years old	123	66.1
22-24 years old	58	31.2
25 years old and above	5	2.7
Program Cluster		
College of Education	65	34.9
College of Business and Accountancy	103	55.4
College of Arts and Sciences	18	9.7
Total	186	100.0

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of first to fourth year male college students which consist of 66.1% or 123 were 19-21 years old. Moreover, the highest number of male college student was from College of Business and Accountancy with 103 participants (54.4%) while College of Arts and Sciences with only 18 participants (9.7%) was the lowest number.

The table reveals that Kabankalan Catholic College's CBA program, specifically Information Technology, has a higher male enrollment compared to other program clusters. In 2017, Information Technology, which is under CBA, was considered the most male-populated program (Medina, 2019). Moreover, the Commission on Higher Education latest record, Academic Year 2021 – 2022, enrollees reached 4,443,217 in all Higher Education Institution all over the country (Vizcarra, 2022). Filipino undergraduate students, aged 18-22, make up the majority of undergraduate students in the country, typically enrolled in first to fourth year programs (Cleofas & Rocha, 2021).

Table 2. Extent of help-seeking behavior of the participants towards seeking professional help

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I would want to get psychological help if I were worried or upset for a long period of time.	4.69	1.73	High
I might want to have psychological counseling in the future.	4.84	1.63	High
If I were experiencing a serious emotional crisis at this point in my life, I would be confident that I could find relief in psychotherapy.	5.08	1.65	High
A person with an emotional problem is not likely to solve it alone; he or she is likely to solve it with professional help.	5.01	1.73	High
If I believed I was having a mental breakdown, my first inclination would be to get professional attention.	4.49	1.69	High
A person should work out his/her own problems; getting psychological counseling would be a last resort.	4.39	1.71	Average
Personal and emotional troubles, like many things, tend to work out by themselves.	4.30	1.64	Average
The idea of talking about problems with a psychologist strikes me as a poor way to get rid of emotional conflicts.	3.74	1.77	Average
Considering the time and expense involved in psychotherapy, it would have doubtful value for a person like me.	4.12	1.65	Average
There is something admirable in the attitude if a person who is willing to cope with his or her conflicts and fears without resorting to professional help.	4.75	1.77	High
Overall	4.54	0.82	High

Table 2 shows the help-seeking behavior of the participants towards seeking professional help. It can be seen that the items “If I were experiencing a serious emotional crisis at this point in my life, I would be confident that I could find relief in psychotherapy”, with a

score of 5.08, and “A person with an emotional problem is not likely to solve it alone; he or she is likely to solve it with professional help”, with a score of 5.0, obtained the highest scores. This implies that men believe that seeking professional help in times of psychological distress is very essential.

On the contrary, the idea in the study of Grewal (2020) that shows a man is viewed as weak if he seeks therapy or makes efforts to improve his mental health is challenged by the data of this study. Which can be seen in table 2, the attitude toward seeking professional help of male college students obtained a score of 4.54 and verbally interpreted as High. This implies, male college student in KCC, in times of psychological distress, would prefer to seek professional help.

It is also notable that items “The idea of talking about problems with a psychologist strikes me as a poor way to get rid of emotional conflicts” and “Considering the time and expense involved in psychotherapy, it would have doubtful value for a person like me”, obtained the scores of 3.74 and 4.12, respectively. This supports the data in the study of Martinez et al. (2020), that Filipino resilience and self-reliance hinders them from asking mental health assistance. Moreover, the perception of seeking psychological help as expensive still serves as a hindrance for male college students in reaching out for a professional when in need, the same result was taken from the study of Shi et al. (2020) in their study of barriers to professional help-seeking in regards to mental health.

Discussion

The study’s principal goal is to understand the extent of help-seeking behavior of male college students. This study used descriptive quantitative research design. The results revealed that male college students opt to seek psychological help when they are psychologically distressed. Moreover, it was also found out that the perception towards seeking help in matters pertaining to the time needed for the process hinders the participants to seek help. In addition, help-seeking inside the institution is free and readily accessible, yet the data gathered shown that participants still thought that to seek help may cost them a lot. Awareness for access to where the participants can seek help could be a great factor of this occurrence. Thus, the study suggests that further investigation discussing the factors of help-seeking behavior of certain population is significant to shed light on this phenomenon. Furthermore, this study highly recommends to all institutions to initiate programs and projects that will help combat the misconception of seeking help to the appropriate professionals in order to continuously promote accessible psychological help to all.

Conclusion

This study aimed to know the extent of help-seeking behavior of male college students of Kabankalan Catholic College enrolled in the Academic Year 2022-2023. Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: In the participants’ help-seeking behavior, it is notable that college student in Kabankalan Catholic College confirms that they would seek professional psychological help when they are in need. On the other hand, the cost and time, for which they think toward seeking professional help greatly hinders them to seek one.

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were formulated by the researchers: The institution, especially the Guidance Office, could formulate programs and projects in promotion of accessible psychological help to all students. This would combat the perception of students that seeking help in the guidance office comes in high cost and would take plenty of their time. As the data presented, students would actually prefer to seek psychological help. Through this, we would encourage the institution to implement once or twice a week a 30 – 60 minutes classroom based formative sessions, which tackles various mental health related concepts such as stress, coping mechanisms, and etcetera. This has been done by the College of Arts and Sciences, and the researchers would highly recommend for its strong and efficient implementation across the college department, and in the institution as a whole. Lastly, this study could be a basis for future researchers to further investigate the various factors affecting the help-seeking behavior of a certain population. The researchers highly encourage the conduct of future studies pertaining to the factors of help-seeking behavior.

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